

Track: Marketing Management

Influence of the New Trend on Consumer Behaviour towards Samsung Galaxy S20

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Abstract:- The key factor of a company is on its marketing campaign; different organizations use different techniques with the aim to withstand the current market competition. As of now, the new trend is showing the world a familiar face which is considered to be a powerful strategy that has been used by the companies. Generally, consumers tend to possess a product to acquire a status around themselves. Hence, their psychological factor relating to status and reputation in the society has taken into account and this has led to the booming of this New Trend Market.

The mobile phone market is creating significant impact on the Indian Economy. The project entitled “Influence of the New Trend on Consumer Behaviour towards Samsung Galaxy S20” is carried out with an objective to determine the consumer preference and level of satisfaction. Though, the features of Samsung Galaxy S20 is comparatively poor than other smartphone brands, the new trend Market of endorsing well-known people has created more demand and increased the sale to a greater extent. Therefore, the research aims to study consumer awareness and find out the problems encountered by the consumers of the Samsung brand.

To conclude the influence of this new trend market, a survey is conducted in Chennai city, among the general audience between the age group of 15 to 55 years in-order to determine the desired results.

Keywords:- Brand, Consumer Behaviour, New Trend, Marketing, Advertising.

I. OBJECTIVES OF RESEARCH

- To study the demographic variables of consumers in Chennai city.
- To study consumer awareness towards Brand and product.
- To find out if there is a positive or negative impact on consumer regarding Samsung Galaxy S20.
- To know about the changes in consumer behaviour because of advertisement.
- To analyse the level of satisfaction towards Samsung Galaxy S20.

- To find out the problems encountered by the consumers of Samsung Galaxy S20.

II. RESEARCH GAP

In today's business world, consumers are getting exploited at a greater extent. Samsung has been involving various kind of strategies, to change the buying behaviour of their consumers. The promotion of Samsung S20 in collaboration with BTS, is at a great hype. Therefore, the target audience are forced to buy products just for their status and prestige in the society. As a result, this new trend has converted their needs into wants. The main aim of this research is to find out if there is a positive or negative impact of consumer regarding Samsung Galaxy S20.

III. INTRODUCTION

The possibility of achieving the targeted goals and objectives of a company is great when there is a powerful marketing strategy in place. One of the recent tactics used by the prominent companies, is to endorse a popular personality in their advertisements in order to attract their target audience efficiently. This has become the most popular tools of promotion and marketing. This strategy is being increasingly used by companies because they could easily reach out to the customers and create a strong impact about their brand and its offerings. This highly helps the companies for a faster growth and expand their products and services enormously.

Although, it might be beneficial on the side of business, but consumers are getting trapped because of this new trend. The buying behaviour of consumers are greatly affected. They are easily attracted towards these advertisement having a well-known face, and they are triggered to buy the product that has been promoted by their favourite people. These products are just being promoted by celebrities, and they do not actually possess the brand or its products in real life. There are also high chances of these products to have predominant issues in its functioning and use. Hence, the customers are said to be the victims for this latest trend in the market.

➤ *Mobile Phone Market:*

Now a days, mobile phone is the most sought after device required by every one for not only communication but for many other uses. The growth of subscription of mobile phone is very high in India, Particularly Smart Phones are in huge demand. This market has been enormously growing in the recent times, because the various mobile phone companies have started to use the new trend, and attract their customers in an effective pre-planned way.

➤ *Samsung – The Brand:*

Samsung was found in 1938. It is said to be a Multi-national South-Korean Company, which was originally created as a trading company. But now, it has a number of holding and subsidiaries companies under the brand name of Samsung. Samsung India has its Headquarter at New Delhi. It has an extensive network of sales offices that are found all over India.

➤ *Samsung Galaxy S20 Series:*

Samsung Galaxy S20, this new series of devices have introduced the latest camera architecture that combines the greatest image sensor of Samsung with AI for brilliant quality. It also includes personalized music features along with console-style games. All these series comes with 5G connectivity, for the purpose of providing a next-generation device with an incredible, AI powered camera and connect with our loved ones more seamlessly

However in the recent years, the competitors of Samsung have increased considerably and this has made the brand very challenging to withstand in the competitive mobile phone market.

➤ *Consumer Behaviour*

Every consumer in the market is different from the other, because each of them have different needs and wants in life. Hence, the factors such psychology, behaviour, preference, taste, motivation plays a major role in buying the products and services. The study of an individual's reason and cause for buying a particular product is known as Consumer Behaviour.

- Psychological factors: The psychology of each consumer differs from the other, therefore the way each one respond to an advertisement depends on their own attitudes, perceptions, and general view of life.
- Personal factors: The demographic variables such as age, gender, profession, customs and culture influences the consumers' interests and opinions.
- Social factors: The consumers' social groups highly varies. Hence, their income and social class plays a major role in influencing the buying behaviour.

➤ *Marketing Affects Consumer Behaviour*

Marketing is a predominant tool that has been effectively influencing consumer behaviour. Marketing campaigns become very effective, because it causes an impact on the consumers and make them react to it. When more people react to these campaigns, the more they will discuss on its brand and products. Hence, this increases the

frequency of purchase of customers, as they are more likely to buy the product which is at a hype. Therefore it causes them to mainly buy products just for the purpose of satisfying their status!

➤ *Current Consumer Behaviour Trends*

It has become very important to study and understand the consumer trends in marketing, because the consumer habits and tastes change from time to time. In this respect, Samsung has been playing an extraordinary role in the current marketing world. On knowing the popularity of BTS they have launched a special series of mobile phones especially for the BTS fans.

IV. NEW TREND MARKET

The idea of new trend market is derived from manipulating the consumer's level of satisfaction mentally but not physically. The company uses their interest in particular field to buy the product which is influencing them with their own bias.

Samsung's objective is to increase brand awareness, brand image and to attract the public's attention, drive's buying decision while focusing on this they are not considering about the consumer issues and feedback.

At the same time, the Chaebol's decision to partner with BTS is looking better and better every single day. The collaboration achieved historic success for Samsung on the social media front, and as things stand right now, Samsung was able to at least partially translate that momentum to premium product sales. Not that it's likely BTS's fandom alone can save the Galaxy S20 line-up from being labelled a failure, but given how 2020 has been panning out so far, it would certainly be unwise to rule out anything.

A. *Issues And Defects:*

➤ *Problem with Smart Unlock*

Many Samsung Galaxy S20 users say that despite having a Smart Unlock set, this feature does not work most of the time when the location is set accurately, like a home or office.

➤ *Android Auto Problem*

Issues relating to Android Auto to work are becoming very common across this new series of Samsung.

➤ *Random Reboots*

Quite a few users are facing the problem of random reboots. In some cases, it is not even random, and the phone restarts every five minutes. It also happens when they unplug wired headphones.

➤ As the battery ages, the chemical reaction no longer completes perfectly, which can result in the creation of outgassing, leading to a swollen battery. Overheating is the major problem faced by Samsung users.

➤ Frequent updates are also an issue. Sometimes after the restart the files remain unsaved or blocked.

V. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- Ahmed et al (2015) concluded that the celebrity ads are more eye-catching than the non-celebrity ads. Consumers also said that the top medium for watching the ads is TV and then the Internet. Results indicate that the celebrity endorsement has sound impact on customers as per their attitude and buying.
- Gauns et al. (2018) stated that most influential celebrity attributes in relation to purchase intentions among state's consumers were likeability, meaning allocation cohesion between the celebrity and the product, familiarity, and similarity. Celebrity attributes such as expertise and trustworthiness are comparatively less significant to affect the purchase decision of Respondents also said consumers that celebrity endorsements influenced them mainly for durable products. Consumers are more attracted if the advertisement involved film celebrities rather than other celebrities.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- *Population*
The population of this study is the general consumers in Chennai city.
- *Sample*
The sample size for this pilot study is 30.
- *Sample techniques*
Simple Random Sampling is used in this study.
- *Data collection method*
The data of this study is collected from both primary and secondary data.
- *Primary Data*
For the purpose of this study primary data was collected from the general consumers in Chennai.
- *Secondary Data*
Secondary data was collected from previous year's research articles and journals.

VII. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A. Classification Based On Age

Table 1 Classification Based On Age

AGE	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS WHO USE SAMSUNG BRAND
15 – 25	17	56.7
25 – 35	9	30
35- 45	-	-
45 – 55	4	13.3
TOTAL	30	100

It is observed that there are 56.7% of the respondents from the age group 15-25 years, 30% from the age group 25-35 years and 13.3% from the age group 45-55 years. The age group of 15-25 years are more likely to use Samsung S20 series.

Hence, it could be concluded that the teenagers and youngsters are very much attracted to purchase this particular model of Samsung.

B. Classification Based On Factor of Purchase

Table 2 Classification Based On Factor of Purchase

FACTOR OF PURCHASE	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
BTS	11	36.7%
BRAND LOYALTY	4	13.3%
PRICE	2	6.7%
LATEST TECHNIQUE	10	33.3%
APPEARANCE	3	10%

It is also observed that 36.7% of the respondents purchase due to BTS, 33.3% purchase due to its Latest technique, 13.3% purchase due to Brand Loyalty, 10% purchase due to Appearance, 6.7% of the respondents purchase due to its affordability of price.

Hence, it could be concluded that the major factor that influences the consumers to buy, is the collaboration of the brand with BTS for the promotion of Samsung S20.

C. Classification Based On Features

Table 3 Classification Based On Features

FEATURES	AGREE	NEUTRAL	DISAGREE
MULTITOUCH SCREEN	30%	26.7%	43.3%
INTERNAL STORAGE	23.3%	25%	51.7%
BATTERY CONTAINS	30%	36.7%	33.3%

It is also observed that:

➤ Multi Touch Screen

43.3% of the respondents are not satisfied with the multi touch screen, the dissatisfaction level of respondents is greater than the satisfaction level.

➤ Internal Storage

51.7% of the respondents are not satisfied with the multi touch screen, the dissatisfaction level of respondents is greater than the satisfaction level.

➤ Battery Contains

36.7% of the respondents are in a neutral state regarding its internal storage.

Therefore, it could be concluded that majority of the respondents are not very much satisfied with the features of this model, Samsung S20.

D. Advertisement Expenses

Fig 1 Advertisement Expenses

As we all know that Samsung advertisements on various platforms are unique. The reason behind their new trend Market by celebrity endorsement which is none other than introducing BTS "Connect BTS" in their ads is a boom to their sales. The fans enthusiastically bought the Samsung's galaxy S20+ and galaxy buds which turned out as one of the best-selling Samsung smartphones of 2021.

The response was crazy in Samsung's turf where both the products went out of stock in just an hour. So even though if it cost 3 billion krw as a Product model and at least 4 billion krw as a brand ambassador or in other words it is equivalent to 3.3 million in US dollars they chose BTS to be their ambassador because their fan base ARMY is proven to be such a powerful fan base.

VIII. FINDING AND SUGGESTIONS

- Consumers are more likely to buy the product just because the product is being used by the famous people.
- The other set of people buys the product for the brand and the rest is for the features.
- The strategy gives immense pleasure to the company which is adversely not good.
- Company focuses on their own success not about the consumer satisfaction and feedback.
- The consumers felt that, the features and parts used in mobile can be improved.
- The company should genuinely advertise its brand and its products without just fantasizing it.
- The company must give an assurance that there will not be this default in future.

IX. CONCLUSION

By this research, it is confirmed that the consumer behaviour is somehow diffused by the advertisement which gives immense pleasure and mental satisfaction. In the case of Samsung's collaboration with BTS, Samsung clearly stated on its website that their latest BTS themed Samsung's galaxy S20+ and galaxy buds was designed exclusively for BTS devoted fan base, ARMY and its limited edition. In fact, the date on which the Galaxy S20 + BTS Edition went on sale on the Samsung website, which is 9 July 2020 coincided with the 7th anniversary of the army. Using their interest towards their bias, Samsung used this opportunity to launch their phones through new trend strategies to bring their brand at the peak of time.

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